

SPECIALIZED BRAIN TUMOR DETECTION SYSTEM FOR SUPERIOR VIEW OF CRANIAL MRI USING AI AND TINY ML TECHNIQUES

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Abstract - With a high mortality rate, brain cancer is considered one of the deadliest cancers in the world and, being the only efficient way of detecting it by doing Cranial Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI), new methods and improvements are needed to reduce the number of people that die from this disease. Following this problem, this research seeks to develop an Artificial Intelligence (AI) developed through Edge Impulse© capable of fastening the process of detecting a brain tumor on the MR scan, which can reduce its mortality rate. At the end of the project, the AI could get an F1-Score of 94.5%.

Keywords: Brain Tumor Detection; Edge Impulse; AI; MRI; Specialist Neural Network.

INTRODUCTION

The brain is the most important organ inside the human body. It controls everything and makes us the humans we are, therefore, it should be the part you must take care of because in the absence of it, even with all the medical technology out there, your body would go into a state similar to a coma (1).

Cancer, in general, is considered the second largest cause of death in the world, accounting for approximately 10 million deaths every year. Of those deaths, 2.5% come from Central Nervous System Cancer and Brain tumors. Even though the data shows it isn't the main cause of cancer deaths around the world, its mortality runs around 81.6% (2). All data and the relationships between them can be seen in Figs. 1 and 2.

Fig. 2. Number of deaths in 2020, both sexes, all ages (2).

Fig. 1. Number of cases in 2020, both sexes, all ages (2).

Unfortunately, the only efficient way to detect this cancer is by doing cranial magnetic resonance imaging (MRI), and in many countries, due to the lack of doctors, this test can take a while till you can do it and get the results out of it (3). Following this idea, and the fact that every single day matters in this type of disease (because it's proven that the faster you get diagnosed, the higher the chances of survival), this project seeks to develop an Artificial Intelligence (AI) capable of doing the first diagnosis of the MRI, fastening the process of detecting a tumor and sending the patient directly to a neuro-oncologist doctor (4).

For context, the concept of AI dates back to 1956 but has only seen decent improvements in the last few deca-

des. Although this time spam seems small, the refinement was exponential through these years and one of the fields that AI researchers have been truly improving in the last few years is the field of medicine. Research done in this area will, without a doubt, lead to new technologies and further improvement on the existing ones, then, fastening the process, lowering the errors and mistakes and helping in general the doctors and medical staff (5).

In short, an AI is composed of an Artificial Neural Network (ANN) composed of Artificial Neurons which are mathematical functions inspired by biological neurons. The graphical representation of an artificial neuron can be seen in Fig. 3 and given by Eqs. 1 and 2.

Fig. 3. Graphic representation of an Artificial Neuron with multiple input (6).

$$n = w_{1,1}p_1 + w_{1,2}p_2 + \dots + w_{1,R}p_R \tag{1}$$

$$a = f(Wp + b) \tag{2}$$

Where $W = [w_{1,1}; w_{1,2}; \dots w_{1,R}]$ is the matrix formed by the weights of the synapses, and b is a bias correction.

Generalizing, one of the main things that change from AI to AI, aside from the data and the “weighs”, is the different mathematical activation functions (f) used in the neurons, in this project, the function used was a variation of the Rectified Linear Unit (ReLU) named Leaky-ReLU (LReLU), both functions faster than the sigmoid function, but, the ReLU function has a disadvantage in which the neurons tend to “die” during training, causing a cascade effect where the neuron’s output start producing only zeroes. On the contrary, the LReLU variation has a parameter that solves this problem (6, 7). Eqs. 3 and 4 represent the equations of the used function and Fig. 4 shows a graphical representation of the same one.

$$a = \text{LReLU}(n) = \begin{cases} \alpha n & n \leq 0 \\ n & n > 0 \end{cases}, \quad (3)$$

$$\text{ReLU}'(n) = \begin{cases} \alpha & n \leq 0 \\ 1 & n > 0 \end{cases}, \quad (4)$$

Fig. 4. Graphical representation fo LReLU function (7).

AI has multiple applications, but the one chosen as best for the development of this research was the Object Detection AI (ODAI), as it can precisely detect any desired object in an image. In the case of this project, the data given was a wide variety of cranial magnetic resonance images with a superior view, and the object selected to be detected was any type of tumor. After a certain time of processing through training and testing, a code capable of detecting a tumor on a brain MRI should be ready (8). The graphical representation of this process can be seen in Fig. 5.

Fig. 5. Graphic Representation of an Object Detection AI (9).

To evaluate an AI, the statistical analysis of binary classification, better known as F-score or F-measuring, can be used. Most AI developers choose to use a harmonic mean of precision and recall called F1 Score, the one used in this project (10).

DEVELOPMENT

In order to develop this research some methods of creating an AI were proposed but, between many different options, the chosen one was Edge Impulse®, a free, easy, and fast-to-use AI development platform (11, 12).

Initially, a database of cranial MRI images with and without tumors was needed. For this, a platform named Kaggle® was a great fit, as this platform is host to one of the biggest AI and Machine Learning (ML) communities in the world, hosting thousands of datasets, models, courses, and other features (13). After searching for “Brain Tumor MRI datasets” on the platform, it was possible to find a decent number of public domain databases (14, 15). These datasets were downloaded and separated into several folders, where the images considered efficient for training and testing the ANN were selected, thus creating a personal database with a wide variety of different images. In the end, the database consisted of 541 magnetic resonance images of the skull from a superior view, with and without tumor. Fig. 6 shows one of the folders containing the selected images.

Fig. 6. One of the folders containing the images of the database.

Back to the Edge Impulse® platform, the first step in developing this Object Detection Artificial Intelligence was importing the dataset to the website server and then classifying the images one by one, marking where the tumor was on the images that had one, and marking nothing on the ones that hadn’t, this way the AI was capable of differentiating the “Background” that was the brain from the “Object” that was the tumor. This process can be seen in Fig. 7, right below.

Fig. 7. Image Classification on the Edge Impulse® platform.

After classifying all images, the database with all the labels is sent to process through training and testing, but first, it needs to set some parameters. For the development of this AI, the KerasCV library and the LReLU function were used, and the final parameters set were a grayscale color depth, an 80%/20% split between training and testing images, 130 training cycles, a learning rate of 0.005 and a confidence threshold of 0.5 (7, 10, 16). A screen print of the Edge Impulse© user's view of the data flow can be seen in Fig. 8.

Fig. 8. Edge Impulse© user's view of the dataflow.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Before reaching the final parameters, several tests were carried out with different parameters and results that had lower precisions than the final one.

With the final parameters set and approximately 20 minutes of waiting, the F1 scores obtained were 94.4% on the Int8 Quantized version (an optimized version) and 94.5% on the Float32 Unoptimized version (17). One thing in common between both versions is that both were 100% capable of totally distinguishing the "Background" from the "Object". The optimized and unoptimized results can be seen in Figs. 9 and 10, respectively.

Fig. 9. Quantized F1 performance stats.

Fig. 10. Unoptimized F1 performance stats.

Upon finishing the development of the AI, the platform gives the option to test the model in some "test images",

and, in this test, the model was able to reach a 90.38% precision, as can be seen in Fig. 11.

Fig. 11. Model testing results.

After the model test, you can check an example of how the AI is working and spotting the desired object, in this case, how the AI is spotting the brain tumor on the MR image. Fig. 12 shows an example of this.

Fig. 12. Example of how the AI spots and classify the tumor on the Cranial MR image with a superior view.

CONCLUSION

In the end, the project results were satisfactory, since the research was done in a few months (considered a short time for scientific research), with a free account on Edge Impulse©, which limits your training time to 20 minutes, then, reducing the number of cycles and learning rate used and, besides all that, the databases were of public domain, coming from different sources with different resolutions and color scales, making it even harder for the AI to process.

Regarding the model developed in this project, and all the disadvantages found through the development, a quantized model, capable of being applied on edge devices, got a 94.4% F1 score. For better context, these scores are higher than multiple similar models done in different research and close to one of the best models made till the time

of this article, the exemplary model was published in Elsevier, a well-known and trustworthy publisher and reached an F1 score of 98.86% (18).

With this type of AI, when applied directly to MRI equipment, hospitals could speed up the process of carrying out these types of exams and make it cheaper to realize it, because it wouldn't need a doctor only to look at the image and detect if there is a tumor or not, then, helping at the same time the hospitals, the doctors and the patients.

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